

THE CONTENT OF DEVELOPING A READING CULTURE AMONG STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Books and the desire to read them play an important role in the activities of students who are stepping into independent life but have not yet fully defined their life goals while striving for intellectual maturity. Unfortunately, however, under the influence of global informatization, the approach to the high spiritual and moral values humanity has revered for centuries has fundamentally changed. The principles of humanity are being rejected, replaced by such negative phenomena as individualism, immorality, materialism, and digital dependence. In the current context, reading serves as a means of fostering students' spiritual and moral education in the spirit of respect for timeless universal and national values. Developing a culture of reading among students is a complex process that requires an integrated approach. The article discusses the process of developing a reading culture among students and its effective organization.*

Keywords: *student, book, reader, reading, reading culture, development, development of reading culture.*

Introduction

It is particularly important to recognise that from the age and psychological point of view, the student period (in most cases, the period from 18-19 to 30-35 years) plays a special role in ensuring personal development and maturity of the individual. Education, especially in higher education institutions, is a complex and difficult process of deep mastering of the basics of professional activity, organization of cognitive activity, timely and high-quality completion of educational tasks. In addition, independent life, solving both educational and social problems that one has to face, and making independent rational decisions on them require students to take a rational approach to the process and organization of their lifestyle. At the same time, the need to allocate time for rest and personal development and the desire to satisfy it encourage students to a critical, analytical and creative approach to their activities. In such a situation, students who do not yet have sufficient life experience turn to fiction (works) as the most honest, ungrateful assistant for themselves.

The most active group of youth in any society is considered to be students. The activity of students as citizens is manifested in the ability to see social, economic and cultural problems existing in society, to understand their essence, to look for solutions and to put forward personal and collective initiatives in this direction. In achieving social activity, in developing as a person, along with a large number of objective and subjective factors, an important role is played by the positive attitude of students to books and their reading. Therefore, in students, as in people of different ages, it is books and their reading that develop spiritual and moral development, a broad outlook, rich imagination, a high level of intelligence (in particular, the ability to think, perceive and reason), emotions and artistic taste.

Meanwhile, it is also vital to acknowledge that reading books has a positive effect on the general psychological, intellectual and even physiological development of a person. This idea is

confirmed by the results of scientific research conducted at a number of universities in the USA. According to Larry Hyell and Daniel Ziegler, reading books has the following effects on the overall psychological, intellectual and even physiological development of a person:

calms the nerves (according to scientists from the University of Sussex (USA), reading books is the most effective way to calm the nerves; it takes only 6 minutes a day);

develops emotions (just like prayer or reading poetry) (a person reading a work of art better understands the feelings of other people in life);

increases brain activity, increases the number of nerve fibers in the brain (according to researchers from Emory University (USA), as a result of reading a book, a person's mental potential is at a high level for several days);

develops communication, listening, writing and creative skills (teachers from Obafemi Awolowo University (USA) found that children develop creative abilities, and indeed, most people who read a lot of books can write poetry, stories, essays or scientific articles at a high level; have the ability to expressively read works of art, especially poems, and perform stage works with high skill);

increases social activity; develops artistic taste;

facilitates the study of foreign languages (helps to easily understand and remember new words when studying other languages);

children who read a lot of books learn lessons better, become good storytellers (the more books are read, the more a person's ability to tell stories improves);

improves relationships between parents and children [9, p. 134].

Developing a reading culture in students is a complex and difficult process. The complexity and difficulty of the process can be justified by the following contradictions:

reading fiction, depending on its genre (for example, reading a story), takes at least 15-20 minutes, while modern youth prefer short videos (the main feature of which is short shots, usually 6 to 60 seconds long; in most cases, such videos are filmed in a humorous manner on everyday topics; they can consist of funny situations or specially played out scenes) [2], a strong need to get acquainted with information on everyday topics, consisting of 2-3 paragraphs;

strong dramatic nature (seriousness) of the plots covered in classical fiction, the desire to understand and feel the mental suffering of the heroes of the work, has been replaced by an interest in small, everyday issues, disputes and conflicts associated with the family life of famous people;

priority of the desire to get acquainted with philosophical views, logical ideas, acquaintance with ideas that do not require reflection, perception, reflection and conclusions, and not organizing their discussion in microenvironments.

In Uzbekistan, a positive attitude towards books and reading them has a centuries-old historical experience not only among individuals but also in society. In the era before the First World War, when there were few literate and educated people, Navoi Khan, Fizuli Khan, Mashrab Khan and Babur Khan gatherings were organized in regions and neighborhoods. In the evenings, when the residents of the region and neighborhood finished their daily work, they gathered in one or another family and read by candlelight the works of such writers as Alisher Navoi, Fizuli, Zakhiriddin Babur, Akhmad Yassawi, Makhtumkuli and Boborahim Mashrab. In this process, literate people from among the gathered read the works and organized group discussions on them.

In some cases, intellectuals who had been trained in madrassas introduced the gathering to the stories of the Koran, the history of the prophets and information on Islamic etiquette described

in the sources. This type of practical movement was consistently carried out in mosques and madrassas.

In the first quarter of a century of the former Soviet Union, attention to books and their reading also decreased in Uzbekistan. The emergence of this negative situation was also influenced by the fact that the spelling in the country changed twice. It was difficult and slow for middle-aged and elderly people to master the new spelling alphabet. Although the new spelling was mastered by young people in a short time, due to their lack of sufficient practical experience, book reading evenings were not organized as before.

In the mid-1960s, the Department of Sociology of Books and Reading was organized in the current Russian State Library [4, – p. 2-3]. As part of the department's activities, the problem of developing a reading culture among the population, including young people, began to be studied from sociological, psychological and pedagogical points of view.

In the 1970s, a tradition of family reading was formed in the former Soviet Union, in particular in Uzbekistan. Among the most important social factors influencing the formation and development of personality, family reading occupies a special place. After all, a child's attitude to books first manifests itself in the family under the influence of parents, grandparents, brothers and sisters. From a historical point of view, family reading has a very ancient chronology.

According to the source, family reading was first introduced into practice in ancient times. According to the testimony of the ancient Greek philosopher Plutarch (Greek: Πλούταρχος), Marcus Porcius Cato (Censor or Censorius), who lived between 234 and 149 BC, created a children's work called "History of Rome" in large letters and read it to his son [10].

Family reading is a family relationship between family members and books, cooperation between children and parents in the joint selection of books, their reading and exchange of opinions about what they have read [7, p. 369].

In most cases, when we talk about “family reading”, we mean reading books by parents or grandparents. However, this is not the case; within the framework of family reading, “children read books to each other, mothers or fathers to children, children to their mothers or fathers, adults to children, and children to older family members (grandparents)” [3, p. 9]. Joint reading of books in the family circle creates spiritual closeness between its members; in the process of reading, there are often cases of feeling and understanding each other’s emotional experiences regarding the reality described in the book, mutual complementarity and support for each other in retelling the plot. In addition, “this increases children’s attention to the book, gives them primary ideas about artistic images, especially about the style of narration” [1, p. 6].

Based on the results of his scientific and pedagogical research, Yu.P. Melentyeva draws attention to the fact that the following four models highlight the essence of family reading:

1. The basis of family reading is the practice of "reading aloud", as opposed to "reading for oneself".

2. The "family reading" model is aimed at organizing not a collective, but a joint movement.

3. The "family reading" model is closely related to such concepts as "personal library", "private library", "home library", "family library".

4. In the "family reading" model, unlike other models, all the functions of reading, including cognition, education, development, recreation and communication, are realized almost simultaneously [5, - p. 11].

Over the past five years, special attention has been paid in Uzbekistan to the revival of the reading tradition in order to educate the younger generation as mature individuals, its comprehensive development, and the formation of a reading culture among the population, including young people. In this regard, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On comprehensive measures to develop the system of publishing and distributing book products, improving and promoting book reading and reading culture" (September 13, 2017) No. 3271 [11], as well as the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic "On approval of the National Program for the Development and Support of the Reading Culture for 2020-2025" (December 14, 2020) No. 781 [12] formed the content of the national policy for the development of the reading culture among the population, especially among young people, and developed a mechanism for the systematic and consistent implementation of this process.

At the same time, it is equally important to the content of the national policy for the development of the reading culture among young people is reflected in the "National Program for the Development and Support of the Reading Culture for 2020-2025" [12]. The national program identifies existing problems in the formation and development of the reading culture. The following problems are directly related to the pedagogical activities of educational institutions:

- there is no system for assessing the effectiveness of measures taken to develop reading;
- the demand for books that contribute to the development of a high artistic and intellectual level of the population, especially young people, has not been studied on the basis of an in-depth analysis;

- there is no systematic propaganda of published books among the population through the media, the organization of creative meetings with authors of books in educational institutions, libraries, courtyards, the formation of a reading culture and reading skills in educational institutions, especially in preschool and primary education;

- ...comprehensive measures have not been developed to develop book reading skills, including electronic ones, among young people from childhood, to improve the reading culture in society [12].

Positively solving the tasks set in the "National Program for the Development and Support of the Reading Culture for 2020-2025", "improving the reading culture of the population, especially young people, widely popularizing reading among them, bringing the reading culture to a level comparable to developed countries, achieving advanced development of the reading culture of young people, improving the quality of human capital due to the growth of their cultural literacy" [12], it has a special pedagogical significance.

The national policy on literacy development serves as a unique methodological basis for organizing social and pedagogical activities in the relevant area in educational institutions operating in the republic.

Development of reading culture among students is a social and pedagogical process aimed at forming a positive attitude of students of higher educational institutions to books (fiction) and their reading.

Successful implementation of this goal requires a positive solution to a number of social and pedagogical tasks. These are:

- strengthening students' understanding that books (fiction), their reading are a means of satisfying their spiritual, ethical, intellectual, aesthetic and even physiological needs;
- strengthening students' positive attitude to books (fiction), their reading;

books (fiction), creation of favorable pedagogical conditions for satisfying students' spiritual, moral, intellectual and aesthetic needs through their reading;

increasing students' interest in reading with the help of effective methods, techniques, means and technologies;

developing students' competencies in making the right, conscious choice of books (works of fiction) for reading, analyzing the content of the read works of fiction, observing them and drawing conclusions using innovative pedagogical forms.

Ultimately, these considerations lead to the conclusion that reading means a person's constant, systematic, consistent and uninterrupted occupation with reading books (works of fiction). The most important thing in this is the ability to consciously and correctly choose books (works of fiction) for reading. Developing students' skills in making a conscious and correct choice of books (works of fiction) for reading requires methodological guidance of this process. Currently, 100 collections of books have been compiled that must be read by students of higher educational institutions of the republic (for example, the collection recommended by the Jizzakh State Literary University) [8]. The collection recommended by the Jizzakh State Literary University includes classical and modern works of world and Uzbek literature, in particular, 66 titles of Uzbek and 34 titles of world literature.

At the same time, in order to ensure that students make an informed and correct choice of a book (work of fiction) to read, they are introduced to examples of literature that reflect universal and national values, based on the recommendations of the most influential world news agencies: Le Monde (France) [17], Guardian [16], Daily Telegraph (Great Britain) [15], BBC news agency [14], Newsweek magazine [18], the New York Public Library [6], which are included in the list of "100 books of the century" (100 books of all time), "10 classic books that changed the world".

When developing a reading culture in students, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

1. Formation of a positive attitude towards reading books. In this regard, using effective factors and efficient methods, it is necessary to develop students' love for books, pay attention to the formation of an understanding that reading is a means of social, spiritual-ethical, psychological, intellectual and emotional development, cognition, perception of being, understanding the essence of interpersonal relations, spiritual-spiritual and other vital needs (including achieving social activity of a citizen, becoming a participant in the communication process). In the context of systematically implemented activities, students develop skills in analyzing the content, main idea, plot, composition, node and solution of a read work of art, skills of perception.

2. Creating an environment that develops interest in books and reading. In this case, it is of great importance to explain the social and individual significance of works of art. The fact that pedagogical activity aimed at explanation is based on inspiring conversations and innovative activities related to reading books guarantees the expected results.

3. Guiding students to choose useful works of art. In this case, works of art are presented to students in accordance with their age, psychological characteristics, interests and spiritual needs, while simultaneously developing their skills in choosing the right book to read. Practical actions in this direction are carried out on the basis of collecting information about the level of interest of students in world and domestic literature, writers and their work, genres that they read with pleasure. Offering works of art taking into account the interests and motives of students has its advantages: the reading process becomes interesting, enjoyable and useful; There is no mental and physical stress (therefore, reading requires mental (organization of thought processes, work of

brain cells, concentration, understanding of the essence of ideas and plots), physical (sitting for a certain period of time, correct posture), hygienic (holding a book at a certain distance, at an angle, observing the time limit, reaction to the lighting of the room, audible noise, etc.), on the contrary, the existing stress is eliminated; their spiritual need is satisfied; there is an opportunity to enter into a dialogue, which is a natural human need (discussion of what has been read); the reader begins to understand the mental experiences of others, empathy for them arises.

4. Encouraging active students to read. With the help of various diagnostic methods (questionnaires, question-and-answer conversation, conversation, interview), quiz, essay, debate, presentation, etc., actively reading students are encouraged to identify; mechanisms for their reward and recognition are developed.

5. Using innovative technologies in the popularization of reading. In today's rapidly the developing era of electronic and Audio books make it easier for students to access and read them. Therefore, when forming a reading culture among students, providing them with information about modern technologies that facilitate reading, in particular, online book clubs, mobile applications, and explaining the procedure for using them will ensure their effective use.

6. Gaining experience in allocating time for reading books. Consistent organization of "Reading Time" outside the classroom allows students to gain experience in allocating time for reading books. In this case, special attention should be paid to the consistent, continuous and systematic organization of the event. Therefore, only then will students effectively form the expected experience. Regularity, consistency and continuity should be based on the organization of "Reading Time" every three days or once a week. The event should include reading can be carried out by a student with correct pronunciation, pleasant intonation and expressive reading skills both continuously and sequentially, a group of students and a team. Enriching the reading time with dialogue (questions and answers) through certain breaks and short pauses will ensure greater effectiveness of the event. At the same time, accustoming students to daily reading at least 5-10 pages of an interesting work of art with the help of various psychological and motivational trainings will lead to the expected success.

Taking everything into account, it can be concluded that for centuries, books, in their functional capabilities, have been a means of providing information about the past, present and partly predicting the future. Books introduce a person to social existence, its structural foundations, help to determine his civic position, principles of development, clarify his life aspirations and strengthen his goals. Under the influence of global informatization, such a high value as reading a book, the approach to spiritual and moral value has radically changed. Nevertheless, as a result of the strengthening of individualism, immorality, greed for materialism, digital dependence in society, the population, including students, has a spiritual and spiritual need to read books. The formation of a reading culture among students is a complex process that requires an integrated approach. In modern conditions, under the influence of socio-pedagogical activities aimed at a specific goal, reading books should become one of the important conditions for the activities of students striving for intellectual maturity.

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